

Indian Buddhist Heritage in Vietnamese Culture – A Sustainable Basis of Vietnam-India Relations

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Abstract

India - a subcontinent of culture, philosophy and religion. It has been one of the centers of civilization since ancient times. Along with the other civilization centers, Indian civilization has flourished and spread to surrounding countries, especially Southeast Asian countries, including Vietnam. It has become one of three solid foundations which has formed the Southeast Asian culture, including Vietnamese culture, the diversity and unity – Unity in Diversity. That's why Vietnamese culture has reprinted many imprints of India's cultural heritage. One the most influenced Indian heritage is Buddhist heritage. It is not only a foundation (basis) for the evolution of Vietnam-India relations in history, but it is also a basis of the especially trusting friendship between Vietnam and India now and in the future. In the framework of a scientific conference, I would like to express my thoughts on the meaning of Indian Buddhist heritage in Vietnamese culture, so that we can further recognize the reasons and deep foundations that make up the Vietnamese-Indian friendship today.

Keywords: *Indian Buddhist heritage, Vietnamese culture, Vietnam-India relationship.*

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Indian Buddhist Heritage

Cultural heritage is the material and spiritual values left by the previous generation. These are the cultural values of the whole world or a nation, an ethnicity left for the future. Cultural heritage includes physical (material heritage) and intangible heritage (spiritual heritage): ideology, philosophy, religion, education, ethics... Material cultural heritages are artifacts that previous generations have left to the country, the ethnicity, the world as works of art: architecture, sculpture, painting, cuisine ...

Buddhism was a religion which was born in India in the 6th century B.C, founded by Crown Prince Siddhartha Gautama of Kapilavastu (in present-day Nepal). In fact, this was a struggle between

two classes in the ancient Indian society, the Kshatrya (fighter) class, against the Brahmin (Clergy) caste in Indian society in the form of religion, ideology and peace, to demand equal rights in Indian society at the time of strict caste division.

Brahmin is a religion that was born in India in the 8th century B.C, to be an ideological tool for the dominance of Brahmin caste of Aryan. The Aryan, when dominating India, divided India into four major classes: Brahmin (Clergy), Kshatrya (Fighter), Vaishya (commoner) and Sudra (outcast) From the perspective of the Brahmanism, Brahma is a supreme God who created all the speices and castes in India. Therefore, people who want to be free or live a happy life must worship Brahma. Brahmanism

spreaded, which was a tool to protect India's caste regime since 1500 B.C. For that reason, in the 6th century B.C, because of the development of production force in Indian society, the Kshatrya class has risen. They had the power of economy, so they did not want to be ranked after the Clergy class anymore and wanted to struggle to affirm the role of their class, and also wanted to fight against the Noble Clergy for social equality. Their struggles are expressed in religious colors. This is the actual condition of history for the birth of Buddhism. The victory of Buddhism has created new cultural and human values for India.

Buddhism has marked on the human spiritual culture the profound, sublime and mysterious values. If Western philosophy is the direction towards the natural world, it is the idea of conquering nature of man. If Chinese philosophy is primarily about the relationship of man to man in society, Indian philosophy is the direction towards the human interior, the study and reflection of man himself. India is a philosophical multi-religious country that almost all have a common substim to learn about the liberation of man himself, to direct people towards goodness in order to free themselves from all suffering. This is expressed in Buddhist philosophical thought itself, of human life and the world view. Each Buddhist doctrine is also the expression of a philosophical thought on how to be free - liberate - resolve the contradictions of each person in a miraculous way.

The greatest miracle of Buddhist doctrine is in "The Four Noble Truths" (the four marvelous truth), are: The truth of suffering, The cause of suffering, The cessation of suffering and The path to the cessation of suffering.

The truth of suffering: the truth is about the human suffering. Buddhism is aware of the human suffering as being created by man himself. People suffer from the torment is a certain: birth, old age, illness, death: DUKKHA (Suffering); desire but cannot have: DUKKHA; to be associated with persons and things that one dislikes: DUKKHA; Love but cannot live together: DUKKHA; Five human physical and

mental elements which exceed the limit: DUKKHA.

The cause of suffering: is the cause of human suffering. The Buddhist perspective believes that people are in a state of depression that is caused and created by man himself. Because man is Ignorance, he is immersed in the delusions of instinctive desires of all human beings: Love, Hatred, Happiness, Anger.

The cessation of suffering: is the truth about how to eliminate human suffering. Buddhist doctrine advises people to know Selflessness to eliminate Ignorance. That means people must not be GREED, ANGER, DELUSION. Because delusion is the source of the suffering that man himself creates for himself.

The path to the cessation of suffering: is the truth of the paths to eliminating suffering. Buddhist doctrine state the "EightFold Path" means the eight paths that man needs to take to lead to liberation. That is: right opinion (with the right point of view, the right mindset); right thinking (with the right perception); right language (correct speech); right action (right action, doing the right thing); right behavior (absoquising desires, maintaining precepts, living right: humane, altruistic); right effort (training to progress every day); right mindfulness (always alert - constantly awake, focused); right concentration (focus on an object to reach the mentalstate...)

The sublime and magical nature of Buddhist doctrines, although it is impossible to fully understand, but in general, Buddhism has created great human values: compassion, equanimity, and spiritual cultivation, cultivating oneself, accumulating virtue, creating good conditions for worldly life, to send love between people and people, the spirit of equality, tolerance, perseverance in the truth and love of peace.

Whether in the primary Buddhism (Theravada) or Mahayana Buddhism, the values of Buddhist human beings have helped us to understand and know how to shine a light on each person's own inner self. Thanks to this, each person knows how to adjust behavior, thoughts, emotions ...

correctly to create good values for himself and society.

In addition to the views on human beings, the Buddhist world view has also shown us great values, which since its inception have become increasingly relevant for the way of viewing the world:

The core content of the Buddhist world view is expressed in the views of the world as follows: Dependent Origination, Impersonation, Impermanence ...

Buddhism believes that the world is created by the Reason and Cause. Dependent Origination: The Twelve Links of Dependent Origination is the Buddha's witness to the world and humanity.

All Indian Buddhist doctrines have been instilled in the Indian people, so that together with the philosophical thoughts and doctrines of other religions make up the "Indian spirit". That spirit is the essence of Indian culture, the Indian cultural identity. That identity is brilliant, it has a strong spread not only in India but also to the surrounding countries. Since the 7th century, although Buddhism has almost declined in India, giving way to Hinduism, it has had a strong spread and vitality to south Asian, West Asian, Northeast and Southeast Asian countries.

Vietnam has been receiving Buddhism since the 2nd century. Buddhism was introduced into Vietnam by peaceful way, following Indian and Chinese merchants and monks.

In this article, we have not talked about the path of Buddhist integration from China to Vietnam, we only want to limit the issue of the introduction of Buddhism from India to Vietnam, the acquisition of Indian Buddhist culture to create Vietnamese cultural heritage.

At the beginning of AD, during India's strong trade with areas in the world such as the Middle East, the Mediterranean ... there is a need for raw materials from the neighboring Eastern countries. They went to Southeast Asia, to Giao Chi (Vietnam belonged to Han) and then back to China. On their way back to India, they set foot on the land of Giao Chi, went to the land of Luy Lau and stayed there, worshipped Buddhas, chanted while waiting for the Northeast

monsoon to come down to return to India. So they created here the first Buddhist center in Vietnam. Buddhism is spread into Vietnam along that path. Since the second half of the 2nd century, Luy Lau has existed as an important and prosperous Buddhist center. Meanwhile, Confucianism in the Han Dynasty.

Indian Buddhist Heritage in Northern Vietnamese Culture

Most of the researchers' opinions say that Buddhism brought to Vietnam from India early on. While in China, due to the influence of Buddhism in the early centuries AD, hampered by Confucianism and Taoism was more difficult. And in Vietnam, Han people also have to use the theory of "Tiger transformation" to easily do this work¹. Meanwhile, in China, it was difficult to integrate Buddhism, and in Giao Chau at that time, Buddhism was very easy to penetrate, the doctrines of Indian Buddhism were very close to their folk beliefs.

There are two very important materials for the very early origin of Buddhism introduction from India into Giao Chau of Vietnam. It was the book: Theory or Explain (理惑論) of Mau Tu (牟子) (165-170?) that was written in Giao Chi during that period, rather than written in the Han interior at the time. The second base was in the 2nd century, in Giao Chi, there was a sangha including 500 and about 15 sets of scriptures, while in the 3rd century in Han there was a sangha. This proves that from the Buddhist imports to Vietnam is from India, through merchant boats carrying Indian monks. They have both helped merchants in their rituals and religious practices, on the other hand, they have also helped merchants feel more secure in the process of floating at sea to trade. In general, in the course of their work, Indian monks brought into Vietnam Buddhist activities and doctrines. Buddhism has been seen by the indigenous peoples as good and culturally integrated, so it has received and adapted to it in a natural, peaceful way.

Giao Chi is considered as a land which was formed in the early stage. It was the first cradle of Vietnamese civilization. In this place did have the indigenous beliefs. They worshipped the

Sun, according to their beliefs, The Sun is the mighty God, understand everything and see clearly the good-bad person, so God punished the wicked people and help the poor¹... It is also from that folk belief that the People in Giao Chi were able to easily receive the Buddhist Theory of Cause and Effect - Karma - Samsara. In addition, they also worship other gods such as the God of Thunder, the God of Rain...as the God's followers. At the same time, they also believe in the souls of the dead that still exist around them to support their families and themselves. Therefore, the Giao Chi people will easily receive The Theory of Samsara - the karma of Buddhism. The People in Giao Chi are also very confident in the origin of their Dragon - Fairy. At the same time, in this early period, Buddhism from India was able to penetrate the North of Vietnam naturally. By this nature, Buddhism is deeply ingrained in, rooted in thought, spirituality, habits in their spiritual life, because they have not been affected by Chinese impositions like Confucianism or Taoism. The harmony between the existing indigenous beliefs and the cultural activities and basic doctrines of Buddhism was formed on a popular type of Buddhist belief in the first years of the Calendar.

Even if Chinese has been imposed on education in Giao Chi and Cuu Chan since the Time of Shi Xie (士燮), it is also a more effective means for people to copy the Buddhist Sutras and learn the Buddhist Sutras through Chinese, making Buddhism even more strong during the colonial period of Northern feudalism in the North and North Central Vietnam. The birth of Theory or Explain (理惑論), or the Forty two Scriptures Chapter, which is written in Chinese, but the

spread of Indian Buddhism to Vietnam – are concrete evidence of this claim.

The first Buddhist scriptures were translated from Sanskrit to Chinese as "Four Decades" to serve the study of mourners or monastic people, rather than Buddhists in folklore. Thus, the integration and shaping of Buddhism during this period was more in-depth academic. For example, the concept of Buddhas continues the popular beliefs about Buddha in the last century, but there has been a bit more Han color than the previous primitive period, when the philosophical and moral and political concepts of Confucius and Laozi were included. Regarding the Dharma of Buddha, if in the Buddhist intellectuals, there is a way of conceptualizing close to "Tao", then in the popular Buddhist world, the Dharma is still a Buddha's magic: three- Refuge (Refuge Buddha, Refuge Dharma, Refuge Sangha), five precepts (5 prohibitions: no killing, no robbery, no fornication, no drunkenness, no lying, offerings to monks and giving... Monks consider religion to be the Buddha's teachings on Impermanence, Selflessness, Discipline - Meditation - Wisdom, Nirvana practices. The concept of the Sangha (the man who is renounced) must implement 250 precepts, shave his head, apply gold, give up property, alms and religiousization (at this time there is no Nuns – the woman who is renounced).

At this time, Nirvana was considered the purpose of the renounced people. According to Theravada Buddhism, Nirvana is considered a "realm", a mental state that man reaches "EMPTINESS". In there, man is completely liberated: no birth, no destruction. Each monastic person maintains the Discipline -

¹At that time in Eastern Han, Taoism also had many fairy elements. The story of "Tiger Transformation" is that Laozi after being separated in the West went to Ho (India) to educate and conquer the Ho people, and he himself became Shakyamuni Buddha (Le, 2015).

The Ancient people in Giao Chi conceived Buddha as a BUT, who had magic, heard and knew everything like God, but he was not high up but was close to everyone. The Buddha appears in many forms to save people, helps life. He loves people but doesn't punish the wicked as God does. The Buddha is an expression of the concept of Dharma during this period. These are the magic of the

Buddha, which are the things that the residents of Giao Chi believe and follow the Buddha, such as reading the Three Rules, offering, giving alms ... Dharma is also a belief in Karma, reincarnation, eternal soul. The People's conception of the Sangha at that time was only in the sangha, not the Sangha. These are monks who wear yellow robes, shaved heads and give up their families and possessions, worship the Buddha, read the Sanskrit. They also believe and follow the concept of compassion, merit. To do good for the next life is to give food to the sangha, to give to the poor. Besides, the concept of appetency limitation is also in the reduction of your own enjoyment to share with the needy (Le, 2015).

Meditation - Wisdom in order to achieve that realm. This has also spread a broad message in society that the direction to achieve the goal of making each person focus on good values, worship good values to follow good values and create good values for themselves and society. Even the concept of Nivarna is not like the distant Heaven of other religions such as Catholicism or Islamism, but it is within each person himself. The originally primitive Buddhism from India also specified that every human being has an available "Buddha of Life". When practicing for a long time, they will gradually become enlightened Buddha nature... From there, each citizen will see the monks and obey, do good and keep morality faithfully.

Buddhism in this period (2nd century B.C), in Giao Chau when influenced by the Indian Buddhist concept has also created another value, which is the "Spirit of sociability" doctrines. Buddhism came from India to penetrate here peacefully, peacefully, without the opposition of folk beliefs. For Chinese Confucianism and Taoism to come at the same time, Buddhism must also struggle for influence, but unlike struggle by imposing, Buddhism chooses the method of peace, harmony, patience of truth, nonviolence. This comes from the open-minded spirit of Buddhism. Therefore, people in Vietnamese society at that time also knew how to PRACTICE follow the Buddhist policy to "communicate" and not "confront" other ideologies. The result of this spirit is that "Buddhism-Confucianism-Taoism " together sociable and develop in Vietnam; Buddhism, by the tools of Confucianism and Taoism, has been widely spread, not only benefiting Buddhists, but also making the followers of Confucianism and Taoism also gradually see the depth of Buddhism. This is the success of Buddhism on the way to spreading into Vietnam.

Thus, when Buddhism from India spreaded to Vietnam, in the early period (primitive), Buddhism was naturally received by the Vietnamese people, blending in with the concept of indigenous beliefs, to create new values in the spirit, The culture and morality of the Vietnamese people. The invasion of Northern feudalism in this period, although it has deliberately brought to our country an

imposition of thought, education, culture ... but it also makes Buddhism from India to be absorbed more quickly by Vietnamese residents through Chinese, making Indian Buddhism spreaded faster and deeper in the North and North Central Vietnam (Giao Chi and Cuu Chan). The appearance of the monks, along with the strict rules on disciplines, has also created trust, helping the Vietnamese spirit to gain new values in their spiritual life as well as their social life. This also means that the Indian Buddhist cultural values and the indigenous cultural values of Vietnam during this period create immortal spiritual heritage.

Indian Buddhist Heritage in the Southern Vietnamese Culture: Funan's Culture

In the present-day Southern region, there once existed an ancient kingdom from the 1st to 7th centuries with the name Funan. During their existence, the inhabitants of Funan have deeply influenced Indian culture, including Buddhism. Buddhism from India was introduced to Funan quite early and developed strongly in the IV - VI centuries, to become one of the major Buddhist centers of Southeast Asia. Buddhism, together with Brahmanism and Hinduism, contributed to the characteristics of the culture that researchers call "Oc Eo culture" or "Oc Eo culture - Funan".

Buddhism has left many imprints in monuments, sites, archaeological artifacts and has been verified for more than half a century.

The formation, development and decline of the Kingdom of Funan took place from the early centuries AD, a time when the territories of Southeast Asia, the "pre-state" societies of the communities of this region, including the South, faced many new challenges, there are also new opportunities to develop (Kiem, 2009).

Probably since the 19th century B.C, South Asian and Indian merchants followed the road from the path of the Himalayas to Myanmar by land, then by waterway from the basins of rivers such as the Irrawaddy, Menam and Mekong, by sea from the Indian Ocean to Southeast Asia, to the Oc Eo of the Funan Kingdom.

For that reason, the Kingdom of Funan since its inception has rapidly developed with the development of the trade route from India, then

the West came, from the North. Therefore, the missionary and pervasive path of Indian Buddhism also achieved many achievements in the Kingdom of Funan (Luong, 2005).

Through bibliography and inscriptions, some people believe that, in the 2nd century, Buddhism in Funan has passed the period of indoctrination, which means that it has been introduced and made development steps, making a mark in social life besides Brahmanism

The Indian Buddhist heritages in Funan are not clearly divided into two categories: tangible culture and intangible culture, but they blend together, creating unique cultural values of Funan.

Specifically: in 484, during the 2nd Vinh Minh dynasty, Southern Qi (479 - 501), the Funan king Jayavarman (484 - 515) commissioned an Indian monk, Sakya Nagasena (Sa Ky Na Gia Tien). Go to Southern Qi to give a speech with humility, asking the Emperor of China to consider the cultural customs and help the Buddha Dharma flourish because the number of monks and nuns practicing is increasing, and the Dharma practice is expanding more and more...

And King Jayavarman devoted the Emperor of China with a golden Dragon King statue, a eucalyptus Buddha statue. After the End of the Southern Qi, the Liang Dynasty was established (502 - 556), in 503, The Ta Tram Ma again sent an embassy to offer tributes. On this occasion, King of Liang ordained The Ta Batsman of An Nam General Phu Nam Vuong. The envoys continued to be sent to China in 511, 514 (Tran, n.a.).

Along with the very developed Hinduism in Funan, Buddhism also flourished here in the 5th and 6th centuries and left many vestiges in the Cuu Long Delta. Many wooden, stone and bronze Buddha statues have been found in the relics of the Oc Eo culture in Kien Giang, An Giang, Hau Giang, Dong Thap, Vung Tau, ... The book "Funan's Buddhism" also affirms: "In terms of the religion of Funan, first according to Brahmanism, later Buddhism was also in vogue;

moreover, Funan was then a major Buddhist displacement station moving to the East"²

Archaeologists (world and Vietnam), while excavating sites of Oc Eo culture on the Southern land, have discovered many Buddha statues and artifacts related to Buddhism First of all, the Buddha and Bodhisattva statues (exquisite sculptures in a fairly large number) were found and published by J. Boisselier in 1966, such as: Avalokitesvara (the statue of The Bodhisattva found in Rach Gia), the Buddha statue sitting in the inter-flowered place in Thang Tam (Vung Tau), dating back to the 6th semi-century, the Avalokitesvara statue found in The Lo Gom Creek (Cho Lon), is the peak of style and sculpture of Funan. In addition, there are a number of Buddha statues discovered and kept at the Ho Chi Minh City Museum such as:

Buddha statue (registration number BTLS.1615) is star wood, black brown, 2.44m high, 0.65m horizontal, in a standing position on the Buddha's throne, the right leg is slightly constricted, the hips of the statue are skewed to the right (17). The statue was dated to the 5th century. This statue was discovered by Louis Malleret on November 3rd, 1943, while excavating at Sa Dec – Dong Thap.

Buddha statue (registration number BTLS. 1617) is poon wood, black-brown, 1.70m high, 0.41m horizontal, in an upright position on the Buddha's throne, dating back to the 5th century (18th century). The statue was discovered and excavated by archaeologists in Loi My village, Phong My ward, Sa Dec - Dong Thap and was returned to the Museum on April 8th, 1937.

Buddha statue (registration number BTLS. 1618) is star wood, black-brown, 1.03m high, 0.35m horizontal, in a standing position on the Buddha's throne, the right leg is upright, the left leg is slightly constricted, the hips of the statue are slightly skewed to the right, dating back to the 7th century. The statue was discovered and excavated by archaeologists in Binh Hoa district, Long An province.

All three statues are Shakyamuni Buddha, influenced by Indian Buddhist sculpture quite

² Nen Chua (1982 – 1983), Oc Eo (1944, 1883, 1884, 1993), Go Thap (1984, 1993), Da Noi (1985), Cay Gao

(1986 - 1987), Go Roc Chanh (1986), Dong Bo (1987), Go Thanh (1988) (Luong, 2005).

clearly and shown on "indigenous" materials with high artistic creativity. It can be said that these wooden Buddha statues are unique sculptures created by ancient residents of the Mekong Delta river and contributed to the quintessence of Vietnamese Buddhist art right from the early centuries AD.

After 1975, archaeologists discovered a series of Buddha statues quite typical of the Funan culture. Especially recently, the Go Thap Relic Site Management Board coordinated with the University of Social Sciences and Humanities of Ho Chi Minh City to organize archeology and excavate 3 times at 3 locations: Minh Su mound, in the burial site and Dia Phat-Dia Vang area in relic site, many more types of relics and cultural relics of Oc Eo culture have been discovered in Go Thap. When excavating in the Dia Phat - Dia Vang area, archaeologists have discovered relics of pottery, stoneware, thousands of fragments, especially discovered a wooden Buddha statue dating back to the 2nd – 4th centuries; the excavation of the burial site discovered 3 types, including the residence site, which is a population of early Hindu and Buddhist temples. Many temples have typical cultural characteristics of the Oc Eo period in the 3rd to 7th centuries.

In the Go Thap relic site, in addition to the residence site at the foot of Minh Su mound, there are also a number of other sites such as Ba Chua Xu temple, Doc Binh Kieu tomb area, a few small mounds around... archaeologists have found many wooden Buddha statues and there were signs of a workshop specializing in the production of these statues. The dates of these

³ In his research project, Dr. Thong Thanh Khanh confirmed: Funan Buddhism is considered the earliest present in the Southeast region, especially Mahayana Buddhism. In fact, even in one name, the Vo Canh inscription of the 1st century AD mentions a dynasty called Srimara which partly reflects the role of Mahayana Buddhism in this "country of Funan". Srimara or Srimala is the name of a Mahayana Buddhist sutra that talks about the role of the five precepts. The full name of this sutra is Srimala - Sim-hanada - Sutra, translated into Chinese as Thang Man Su Tu Hong Nhat Thua Dai Phuong Tien Phuong Quang sutra, commonly referred to as the Thang Man Sutra. The main content of this sutra is about lady Thang Man, whose personality symbolizes the absolute equality of the Mahayana Buddhism spirit, the

settlements range from the late prehistoric period to the Oc Eo culture period.

“Many wooden Buddha statues were discovered by accident while digging, farming in large numbers, the richness and variety of sizes and designs both reflect the absorption of new artistic influences and reveal the genuine and simple indigenous features in the sculpture material is an abundant source of wood materials. The poon wood material that makes these statues is both sustainable and satisfying the creativity and diversity of artisan Oc Eo, creating a unique art style here. The 5th-7th century was a period of brilliant development of indigenous Buddhist sculpture, which is an example of the collection of wooden Buddha statues in the Dong Thap region (Le, 2015).

From the point of view of most researchers, it is not possible to determine with certainty or exactly when Buddhism was introduced to Funan from India, but when Buddhism entered Funan, it had already passed the propagating period. That is, it has made its mark on this kingdom through a series of artifacts that archaeologists and cultologists have found in the ruins of the ancient kingdom of Funan. Buddhism was introduced to Funan before the 2nd century³ (evidenced by the Vo Canh stele, although it did not belong to the Southern region, it also proves to us about this date). The Buddha statues found in the area of the Dia Phat – Dia Vang of Go Thap relic site (Dong Thap) dating from the 2nd to 4th centuries are fundamental proof of the introduction of Buddhism from India. Entering Funan has passed the stage of propagation, so they have left

Avalokitesvara Bodhisattva's motherhood. The Avalokitesvara Bodhisattva is not a path reserved only for sages, great men, or any special kind of person, because buddha nature is inherent in all humankind. That aspiration and responsibility are fully expressed in the personality of a Buddhist woman. With the motherhood, the Avalokitesvara Bodhisattva embraces the whole world in her tremendous tolerant embrace. Thang Man is a guide to the methods of raising the Avalokitesvara Bodhisattva's holy pregnancy, expanding her tremendous motherhood, so it's not only for women, but also the Avalokitesvara Bodhisattva's path. Thus, the personality of Thang Man and the principle of Thang Man are included in the title of the sutra. (According to Tran Thuan – Op cit).

these special heritages in the culture of Funan - Southern Vietnam in particular and Vietnamese culture in general.

In Funan, Mahayana Buddhism and Theravada Buddhism coexist. Therefore, there was a statue of Avalokiteśvara Bodhisattva found in Rach Gia that confirmed this. In addition, pho in the South also discovered an inscription on gold leaf in Go Xoai (Long An) about the Dharma body shelf, a document written in Pali language (hybrid Pali), with traces of Sanskrit and literature Deccan order (South India)⁴. Although this inscription dating from the 8th or 9th century, after the destruction of the Funan kingdom, can be classified as a "post-Funan culture", it can be seen that the inscription could not belong to the Khmer because the Chenla at that time were Brahmin. After defeating Funan, the Chenla advocated bringing Brahmanism to the forefront, Buddhism remained only in the folk. In the book Nam Hai, the story of Dharma Master Nghia Tinh, it is written: "Chenla under the reigns of King Bhavavarman I and Mahendravarman both followed Brahmanism. Buddhism was persecuted." It seems that the inscription at Go Xoai may be a continuation of the spirit of the "Dharma body shelf" of the earlier Funan people⁵.

Besides the inter-existence of Theravada and Mahayana Buddhism, there is the interweaving of Buddhism with Brahmanism and Hinduism in the Oc Eo culture that we can easily recognize. Besides, Buddhism, when imported from India to Vietnam, has also adapted and combined with indigenous elements to create outstanding cultural values of Funan Buddhism, very unique. That is reflected in many aspects, especially in

⁴ This inscription was made by the Archaeological Center - Institute of Social Sciences in Ho Chi Minh City. Ho Chi Minh City combined with Long An Museum to organize excavations, and Sanskrit antiquities have translated and published. Dr. Thai Van Chai translated and published after discovering, then in 1993, Prof. Ha Van Tan translated and published in the announcement at the September 1993 Archeology Conference.

⁵ Recently, in a Champa relic in Gia Lai province, behind a relief with a sitting Buddha image on it, which Bui Minh Tri announced in 2012, there are 4 lines of inscriptions like the Go Xoai inscription, written in standard Sanskrit and in an older script, about the VI – VII centuries, differing only in the Mahāvastu in a few points. And so, up to now, the verse of Dharmakaya has been found in Pali as well as in Sanskrit in many parts of Vietnam, especially in the

the Buddha statues found in many places in the South, in terms of materials, manufacturing techniques, art styles, etc....

When studying the heritage of Indian Buddhism in Funan culture, anyone can clearly see that Buddhism has merged with Brahmanism and Hinduism in every breath of life of the inhabitants of Funan, contributing to the characteristic of Oc Eo culture that has existed for many centuries. On the basis of studies on the culture of Oc Eo - Funan shows that this culture is "imbued with the spirit of Buddhism".

At the same time, Funan is not only absorbed and transformed the Indian Buddhist heritage in Funan - Southern Vietnam, but also truly "a bridge" between India and China. Funan Buddhism was received from India, established on the indigenous beliefs and spread to the South China region. It can be seen that Funan Buddhism has many similarities with Champa Buddhism and Giao Chau Buddhism. And it was here that the Chinese people received Buddhist influence from the Funan people. Many Funan monks (including Indian monks) went to China to lecture on Buddhist scriptures and translate Buddhist scriptures for the court; historians came to China to spread Buddhism, many Buddhist scriptures were translated and transferred to China so that the people here could bathe in the Dharma in the spirit of Buddhism (Tran, n.d.).

After a period of flourishing development, in the 6th century, the Funan empire weakened and was defeated by the Chenla people. After a period of resistance, at the beginning of the 7th century, Funan officially belonged to Chenla, ending the existence of Funan as an independent nation, a

southern region. It can be seen as solid evidence of the presence of Buddhism, Mahayana Buddhism. And the relics mentioned in those civilizations must be Buddhist relics.

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powerful empire that influenced not only with Southeast Asia but also make an impression on many countries around the world. Along with the end of the Funan kingdom, Buddhism in the southern region was also interrupted for a long time. In short, it can be said that, following a natural flow of world civilization, right from its birth - around the first century BC or AD, Funan immediately received the values of the world. India's culture follows the caravans of merchants, politicians and monks. Buddhism came naturally to Funan - Southern Vietnam, so, along with the existing indigenous elements, Funan culture has been irrigated with the heritages of Indian Buddhism. Indigenous factors mixed with foreign elements have created rare "identities" of a Funan Buddhist culture. It is unique and separate from the surrounding countries. Manifestations are tangible heritage: Buddha statues, Buddhist temples are blended into intangible heritage through customs, social life, and religious activities that researchers have collectively referred to as Oc Eo – Funan culture. Because of its brilliance, the culture of Oc Eo - Funan has spread and connected with the cultures of Dong Nai - Khmer - Champa - Giao Chi... all the way to China. This also means that even though the Funan kingdom soon perished, the Funan culture still became a link connecting the South Asian Indian culture with the East Asian cultures (Southeast Asia and Northeast Asia). - creating an endless flow of Buddhist culture from the past to the present and the future.

Buddhist Heritage in the Culture of Central Vietnam: Champa Culture

Legend has it that in the early years of AD, in the narrow strip of Central Vietnam today, there were ancient ethnic groups, namely the Cau ethnic group in the South Central region (Kramuka Vamsa) and the Dua tribe (Narykela Vamsa) in the North Central region, living along the central coast. These two ethnic groups were invaded by the North, so they joined together to fight that invasion and win. The first state named Lam Ap (Tuong Lam) was born around the end of the 2nd century. Later there were other names of Lam Ap such as: Hoan Vuong, Chiem Thanh or Champa. But the name Champa is most often called. It is also the name of a beautiful and

fragrant flower of the countries associated with the development of Buddhism in Southeast Asia.

Developed on the basis of Sa Huynh culture, the Cham people have built themselves a native culture, and at the same time have imported external factors - especially Indian culture. Although introduced after Chinese culture, the mark of Indian culture in Champa is very bold. Along with merchant ships, Indian monks also crossed the sea to come here very early. The development of Buddhism in Champa was also proportional to the increase of the trade wave from India through and to Champa, creating a mainstream culture of Champa. For that reason, the Indian Buddhist heritage in Champa is also extremely rich and unique.

As in the North and South, in the Central region, the inhabitants of Champa also received the spread of Buddhism from the routes of gold and commerce. Indian merchants brought monks with them to pray for their safe and successful journeys, and since then Buddhism has followed the monks from India to Champa. The most unique and sharp point in the process of introducing Buddhism to Champa is the harmony and cultural interference between Brahmanism, Buddhism and Hinduism. A main reason is due to the "softness" of the indigenous elements of the Southeast Asian population, but also an important factor is the "subdued" nature of the Sa Huynh culture that existed before the arrival of the Sa Huynh culture and penetration of foreign factors. Therefore, even though the first layer of cultural heritage in Champa was Brahminism, the Buddhist and Hindu heritages were also very bold, making those heritages blend together, creating a perfect harmony. very special whole of Champa culture.

There are comments that: Brahminism is superior to Buddhism in Champa because it has more advantages in the way of organizing and building social structure. But in fact: "Every monk before coming to Champa studied Brahminism...so "Indian Buddhism to Vietnam has both Brahmanism and Buddhism in it and "when it comes into contact to Indian culture, the Cham people were quickly influenced by that culture, in terms of ideology, religion, administration, law, customs and practices, and

writing... Although the main religion of the Cham people is Hinduism, they worship mainly the Three Gods: Brama, Visnu, Shiva, or only one of the three Gods, but they also worship Buddha..." (Phung, 2012).

According to research by domestic and international scholars, Champa culture has been deeply influenced by Indian culture, including Brahmanism and Buddhism, because it is difficult to separate the Brahmin element. Buddhism out of elements of Buddhism in Champa culture. That has been found in historical sources and artifacts - extremely unique material cultures of Champa culture.

Typical is the architectural work "Devil's Tower". According to the "Thuy Kinh Mantra" recorded: in the city of Dien Chong of the Cham people, "Temple of the Devil's Tower has 8 shrines, multi-storey high tower, and the image of the Buddha Tower" (Institute of Archaeology, n.d.). "During the conquest of Luu Phuong (650), in addition to stealing 18 sets of mantras in the temple, all cast in gold, Luu Phuong also collected 1350 copies of Buddhist scriptures wrapped in 564 bundles and written in Cham script. Thoes examples of such historical documents show that Indian culture was present early and played an important role in the social life of Champa" (Phung, 2012).

When studying about the Indian Buddhist heritage in Champa country, we cannot help but mention the monument of Vo Canh stele (Khanh Hoa). According to the researchers, the Vo Canh stele "was written in Sanskrit properly, showing that they were deeply influenced by Indian civilization...the stele composer showed a clear belief in Buddhism. Buddhism" (Maspero, 1928). Because: "The thought that this world is not eternal, the meaning of the transformation from one life to the next, compassion of humankind, the sacrifice of one's possessions for the benefit of others, all those things demonstrate the generosity and tolerance of a descendant of Cri Mara and a clear tendency to Buddhism" (Le, 2012). The date of Vo Canh stele was determined in the 2nd - 3rd century AD.

The discoveries of bronze Buddha statues at Cao Lao Ha (Quang Binh) dating from the 6th - 7th centuries have shown that the influence of

Buddhism on Northern Champa is very clear. In the imperial capital of Shihapura (Tra Kieu - Quang Nam), in 1989 - 1990, 4 terracotta Buddhist artifacts were discovered at the foot of Buu Chau hill - the center of Tra Kieu citadel. It is the image of Buddha sitting in meditation. The date of this group of statues belongs to the 7th - 8th century, consistent with the records of the monk Nghia Tinh when he visited the capital in the year (617 - 695) (Tran, 1993). Buddhism in Champa was represented in the following centuries, with the appearance of Dong Duong Buddhist Monastery. According to inscriptions found in Dong Duong (Quang Nam), King Indravarman II built here a temple and a Buddhist Monastery. Among the large valuable artifacts here, it is worth noting that there is a 1.80m high bronze Buddha statue in the style of Buddha image of Amaravati region. According to J. Boisselier "this statue is certainly, if not an imported work, a work so deeply related to the Indian tradition that it is impossible to detect traces of an indigenous tradition" (Boisselier, 1963). Also here, in 1978, researchers found a bronze statue of Lokeshvara 1.14m high, showing the perfection with the face full of humanity of the Cham people (Le, 2012).

Along with the Dong Duong Buddhist center, many Champa inscriptions also emphasize the nature of Buddhism under the Indrapura dynasty such as the Bac Ha stele (also known as the O Ron - Quang Binh stele) dating from 889 about a big center of Buddhism in the North Champa. Bronze statues of Avalokitesvara found at Thuy Cam - Thua Thien Hue (2 statues), at Dai Huu, My Duc (Quang Binh) (6 statues), or ceramic terracotta with Buddha images found at Choi mountain (Quang Ngai) (Doan, 1993) together with 4 bronze Buddha statues found in Phan Thiet (Binh Thuan) dating back to the 9th - 10th centuries... it shows that Buddhism is very popular in society, especially in the North Champa region. "Nevertheless, in Buddhist centers, the Hindu element is still evident, for the monks themselves are also influenced by Brahminism and Hinduism forming a dominant religion throughout the afternoon. long history of the Cham people" (Le, 2012).

Based on the above evidences, we can assume that Buddhist thought was transmitted and arose

here in the 1st century AD, along with the "blooming" introduction of Indian and South Asian cultures. Indeed, the Central Coast, which has favorable conditions for maritime exploration, has natural seagate that are favorable for ships to shelter, since then, along with prosperous development along with the superiority of the influenced culture is the transformation from the pre-Champa indigenous culture to a Cham culture. That strong impact made a certain influence on religion in this period. Considering the pre-Indian context in terms of religion up to the death of the Buddha, there has been a hundred years of transformation in the monastic community. From the enthusiastic support of the kingdoms, the bourgeois rich and famous. Also from here, the echoes and virtues of the Buddha are still covering the kingdoms, so the issue of respecting the Three Jewels in the absolute spirit is still profound. Since then, the ideas of Arya- Samiti- Nikaya and Sarvativada have developed strongly, many kings who have ruled in favor of Buddhist cults have created a prosperous time. Certainly, the merchants are Buddhists and the priests who follow the footsteps to new lands still carry with them their own indigenous religion and philosophy that they have absorbed throughout Asia. In these tours to exchange goods in response to that growing demand, according to the conditions of each land and favorable conditions of the port, creating a prosperous economy - cultural exchange has had successfully positive achievements: the port of Champa is the place where was attractive to merchants and find the most because of the importance place of goods exchange. It was also a place where some priests recognized and found that this land could be suitable for educating the Dharma and was positively accepted by this community. True Buddhists from time to time wandered to find a secluded place to gather - and at the same time spread enlightenment for sentient beings before BC, and thereby brought the philosophy of Buddhism to the top. Along with the multi-dimensional development of Brahmins, these two religions have begun to be deeply rooted in the thought of the relevant Champa community. Entering the AD period, the perfection of

ideology - religion was confirmed in this land with a feudal country called Champa. A pure flower to offer to the Buddha and the Brahmas (for Brahmins) to officially take the name of this community.

Buddhist Heritage in Vietnamese Culture – One of the Foundations of Vietnam India Rapprochement

It can be affirmed that, right from the ancient times, the values and cultural heritage of India - including the Buddhist heritage - have been "successfully" spread to Vietnam, very naturally and peacefully. That is why "Indian culture is called to a long river that originates in the Himalayas, crosses forests, wastelands, orchards, farms, villages and cities, receiving more tributaries but still keep the same identity" (Various authors, 1996). In other words, Southeast Asia in particular is the second homeland of India and also a place to keep and preserve the traditional cultural values of India" (Ha, 2012) of which Buddhism is one of the three mainstream of Indian culture flows into Vietnam.

The Buddhist heritage has been brought to Vietnam since ancient times and it is constantly flowing, blending into the flow of indigenous culture in Vietnam in all 3 regions: North - Central - South, imbued and blended into Giao Chi, Funan and Champa cultures, creating new, extremely unique and special cultural values of Vietnam. This is one of the foundations that create a strong, solid and long-lasting relationship between Vietnam and India, because that relationship is built and nurtured by cultural heritages and values.

Throughout a long period of ancient and medieval times, Vietnam and India still closely and deeply interact with each other through trade, culture and politics. In the modern period, the process of contact and exchange between the two countries continued to develop and because both countries shared the same fate of being invaded by colonial empires. In the process of finding answers for the way to save the country of their people, patriots and revolutionaries met.

Nguyen Ai Quoc of Vietnam with revolutionary Motilal Nehru – father of Indian Prime Minister

Jawaharlal Nehru. There was a meeting very early because they are both patriots and people, both wanting to find answers for their way of saving the country. Despite being far apart, the Vietnamese and Indian revolutionaries were able to quickly find each other in terms of cultural similarities. Ho Chi Minh, Motilal Nehru, Mahadma Gandhi or Jawaharlal Nehru all embody the good cultural values of the two peoples of Vietnam and India. That's why they were able to quickly understand each other, share with each other, learn from each other the ways and ways to save the country in the common background that both nations are in enslavement. of colonialism. Although the path of national salvation and revolutionary methods of the two peoples of Vietnam and India are different, they both gained independence in the same 40s of the 20th century. Vietnam is an example of India in the revolutionary struggle for national liberation, India is also a lesson for Vietnamese revolutionaries - led by Nguyen Ai Quoc - Ho Chi Minh to refer, learn and apply creatively to the specific conditions of your country and make victories.

Here, the core point of sympathy, sharing and similarity is culture - including Buddhist cultural heritage. Nguyen Ai Quoc – Ho Chi Minh admires Mahatma Gandhi, Motilal Nehru, J. Nehru for the way, the method of “persisting in the truth, non-cooperation, non-violence and peaceful struggle” – which made the success achievements of the Indian revolution in 1947. One of the important reasons for these victories is the heritage of Buddhist thought. During the Cold War period, although the two countries had two different development paths, although there were times when facing obstacles and difficulties, India almost always supported and stood side by side with Vietnam in the two resistance wars and against the French colonialists and the American imperialists. The relationship between the two countries is not limited to the state relationship, but also has a close relationship like a family. After 1975, when Vietnam was completely unified, independent and free, the relationship between the two countries entered a new stage. The Vietnam - India Friendship Association was established, on the basis of which Vietnam became a member of

the United Nations in 1977. These events also showed the sincere affection of the Government and people of the two countries. water for each other. If it is not an understanding and harmony in culture, it will be difficult to have such intimacy.

After the Cold War period, the relationship between Vietnam and India developed positively again, in which cultural cooperation is considered as one of the key spearheads to promote the development of the two countries' relations. In May 2003, the two countries issued a Joint Statement on the Comprehensive Cooperation Framework between Vietnam and India in order to consolidate and develop cooperation in both breadth and depth of strategic nature in the 21st century. The relationship between Vietnam and India was officially elevated to the level of a strategic partnership in July 2007. On that basis, in each field, the relationship between the two countries has been established more comprehensively and deeply with high effective. The Indian government since Prime Minister Narendra Modi came to power has always given special priority to other countries in the Indo-Pacific region, including ASEAN countries and Vietnam. The Look East Policy, Act East and the adjustment of India's foreign policies under Prime Minister N. Modi have demonstrated India's special interest in the region in general and with Vietnam in particular. private. Speaking at the 69th session of the United Nations, Prime Minister N. Modi emphasized: “The destiny of a nation is closely related to its neighbours. That is why the Indian government places a top priority on promoting and cooperating with neighboring countries.” (United Nations, 2014). On the Vietnamese side, it is also trying its best to take advantage of and create many conditions to promote cooperation. with India in all fields.

More and more centers, institutes, etc. for Indian studies have been established in Vietnam; Associations, economic, educational, social, cultural organizations ... between the two countries are also increasingly flourishing. In particular, the Mausam Project was officially announced by India at the 38th session of the World Heritage Committee held in Doha, Qatar in June 2014 (Government of India, Ministry of

Culture, 2014). The project is a cultural connection Maussam (Monsoon) with a connection range extending between East African countries, along the Arabian Peninsula, through southern Iran to South and Southeast Asian countries.

This project has a particularly important place in India's development strategy. This is a complementary project to India's Act East policy in Southeast Asia (Daniel, 2015). Vietnam is one of 39 countries included in this Project. Indian diplomats also frequently mentioned historical, cultural and religious relations that existed in history on the trade, cultural and religious exchange route between India through Southeast Asia. to Vietnam and affirm that these are the foundations of all future Vietnam - India, India - Vietnam relations. The most recent is the back-to-back struggle between the two countries in the fight against the Covid-19 pandemic. Vietnam has been by India's side, India has also always been by Vietnam's side in the most difficult times. of the war. That has proved the increasingly close, cordial, faithful, friendly, trustworthy and sustainable relationship of both nations. The most recent visits of Indian Prime Minister N. Modi to Vietnam and of Vietnamese leaders to India in the midst of a severe pandemic have proved it. The relationship between the two countries has been elevated to the level of a comprehensive strategic partnership in recent years.

Conclusion

Buddhism is an early religion in India in the 6th century BC. It was born in the condition that India's social history at that time was divided into strict castes, the Kshatrya martial arts class in India wanted to fight against the Brahmin rank to assert their role in Indian society as well as spreading equality and peace, wishing for the well-being of each person in their own life.

That is why the teachings of Buddhism are also the philosophical and ethical thoughts of people in society, therefore, although very sublime and magical, the values in Buddhist teachings are also imbued with humanity, was accepted by Indian society as an orthodox religion of India from the 6th century to the 7th century B.C. Since the fall of the Harsha dynasty in India, Buddhism in

India has given way to Hinduism - a religion with Indian characteristics. However, Buddhism has spread widely outside, to the region in South Asia, Northeast Asia, Southeast Asia and to Vietnam.

Buddhism penetrated into Vietnam along the way of commercial and political exchanges, by way of peace. Therefore, the values of Indian Buddhism have combined, harmonized and interfered with the indigenous cultures of Vietnam, to create new cultural values. But the heritage of Indian Buddhism has created tangible and intangible cultural values in all three regions of Vietnam since the first centuries AD. Those are the values of Buddhist culture in Giao Chi (North), Funan (South), Champa (Central) Vietnam. The Buddhist heritages have been closely intertwined, imbued in the spiritual and material life of each resident on the S-shaped land, and at the same time interfere and harmonize with other religions to create the cultural values are extremely unique, unique and lasting in Vietnam.

It is the cultural values created in the Buddhist heritage that have created the foundation and connection between the two peoples of Vietnam - India in history. Through many changes, but those sustainable cultural values have become more and more sustainable roots, the faithful attachment of the two countries throughout the history of the struggle for national liberation and national construction, international economic integration. India and Vietnam have become each other's comprehensive strategic partners now and will continue to develop firmly in the future, with long-standing and sustainable cultural foundations.

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